

Smarandache fuzzy *BCI*-algebras

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Abstract. The notions of a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra (ideal) of a Smarandache *BCI*-algebra, a Smarandache fuzzy clean(fresh) ideal of a Smarandache *BCI*-algebra are introduced. Examples are given, and several related properties are investigated.

1. Introduction

Generally, in any human field, a Smarandache structure on a set A means a weak structure W on A such that there exists a proper subset B of A with a strong structure S which is embedded in A . In [4], R. Padilla showed that Smarandache semigroups are very important for the study of congruences. Y. B. Jun ([1,2]) introduced the notion of Smarandache *BCI*-algebras, Smarandache fresh and clean ideals of Smarandache *BCI*-algebras, and obtained many interesting results about them.

In this paper, we discuss a Smarandache fuzzy structure on *BCI*-algebras and introduce the notions of a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra (ideal) of a Smarandache *BCI*-algebra, a Smarandache fuzzy clean (fresh) ideal of a Smarandache *BCI*-algebra are introduced, and we investigate their properties.

2. Preliminaries

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type (2,0) is called a *BCI-algebra* if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (I) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (II) $(\forall x, y \in X)((x * (x * (x * y))) * y = 0)$,
- (III) $(\forall x \in X)(x * x = 0)$,
- (IV) $(\forall x, y \in X)(x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y)$.

If a *BCI*-algebra X satisfies the following identity;

- (V) $(\forall x \in X)(0 * x = 0)$,

then X is said to be a *BCK-algebra*. We can define a partial order “ \leq ” on X by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Every *BCI*-algebra X has the following properties:

- (a₁) $(\forall x \in X)(x * 0 = x)$,
- (a₁) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \leq y \text{ implies } x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x)$.

A non-empty subset I of a *BCI*-algebra X is called an *ideal* of X if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $(\forall x \in X)(\forall y \in I)(x * y \in I \text{ implies } x \in I)$.

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Sun Shin Ahn¹ and Young Joo Seo²

Definition 2.1. ([1]) A *Smarandache BCI-algebra* is defined to be a *BCI-algebra* X in which there exists a proper subset Q of X such that

- (i) $0 \in Q$ and $|Q| \geq 2$,
- (ii) Q is a *BCK-algebra* under the same operation of X .

By a *Smarandache positive implicative* (resp. *commutative* and *implicative*) *BCI-algebra*, we mean a *BCI-algebra* X which has a proper subset Q of X such that

- (i) $0 \in Q$ and $|Q| \geq 2$,
- (ii) Q is a positive implicative (resp. commutative and implicative) *BCK-algebra* under the same operation of X .

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a *Smarandache BCI-algebra* and H be a subset of X such that $0 \in H$ and $|H| \geq 2$. Then H is called a *Smarandache subalgebra* of X if $(H; *, 0)$ is a *Smarandache BCI-algebra*.

A non-empty subset I of X is called a *Smarandache ideal* of X related to Q if it satisfies:

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $(\forall x \in Q)(\forall y \in I)(x * y \in I \text{ implies } x \in I)$,

where Q is a *BCK-algebra* contained in X . If I is a *Smarandache ideal* of X related to every *BCK-algebra* contained in X , we simply say that I is a *Smarandache ideal* of X .

In what follows, let X and Q denote a *Smarandache BCI-algebra* and a *BCK-algebra* which is properly contained in X , respectively.

Definition 2.2. ([2]) A non-empty subset I of X is called a *Smarandache ideal* of X related to Q (or briefly, a *Q-Smarandache ideal*) of X if it satisfies:

- (c₁) $0 \in I$,
- (c₂) $(\forall x \in Q)(\forall y \in I)(x * y \in I \text{ implies } x \in I)$.

If I is a *Smarandache ideal* of X related to every *BCK-algebra* contained in X , we simply say that I is a *Smarandache ideal* of X .

Definition 2.3. ([2]) A non-empty subset I of X is called a *Smarandache fresh ideal* of X related to Q (or briefly, a *Q-Smarandache fresh ideal* of X) if it satisfies the conditions (c₁) and

- (c₃) $(\forall x, y, z \in Q)((x * y) * z \in I \text{ and } y * z \in I \text{ imply } x * z \in I)$.

Theorem 2.4. ([2]) Every *Q-Smarandache fresh ideal* which is contained in Q is a *Q-Smarandache ideal*.

The converse of Theorem 2.4 need not be true in general.

Theorem 2.5. ([2]) Let I and J be *Q-Smarandache ideals* of X and $I \subset J$. If I is a *Q-Smarandache fresh ideal* of X , then so is J .

Definition 2.6. ([2]) A non-empty subset I of X is called a *Smarandache clean ideal* of X related to Q (or briefly, a *Q-Smarandache clean ideal* of X) if it satisfies the conditions (c₁) and

- (c₄) $(\forall x, y \in Q)(z \in I)((x * (y * x)) * z \in I \text{ implies } x \in I)$.

Smarandache fuzzy BCI-algebras

Theorem 2.7. ([2]) Every Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X is a Q -Smarandache ideal.

The converse of Theorem 2.7 need not be true in general.

Theorem 2.8. ([2]) Every Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal.

Theorem 2.9. ([2]) Let I and J be Q -Smarandache ideals of X and $I \subset J$. If I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X , then so is J .

A fuzzy set μ in X is called a *fuzzy subalgebra* of a BCI-algebra X if $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$. A fuzzy set μ in X is called a *fuzzy ideal* of X if

- (F₁) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$,
- (F₂) $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Let μ be a fuzzy set in a set X . For $t \in [0, 1]$, the set $\mu_t := \{x \in X | \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a *level subset* of μ .

3. Smarandache fuzzy ideals

Definition 3.1. Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a *Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra* of X if it satisfies

- (SF₁) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in P$,
- (SF₂) $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in P$,

where $P \subsetneq X$, P is a BCK-algebra with $|P| \geq 2$.

A map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a *Smarandache fuzzy ideal* of X if it satisfies (SF₁) and

- (SF₂) $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in P$,

where $P \subsetneq X$, P is a BCK-algebra with $|P| \geq 2$. This Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra (ideal) is denoted by μ_P , i.e., $\mu_P : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a fuzzy subalgebra(ideal) of X .

Example 3.2. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra ([1]) with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	3	3	3
1	1	0	1	3	3	3
2	2	2	0	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	0	0	0
4	4	3	4	1	0	0
5	5	3	5	1	1	0

Define a map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) := \begin{cases} 0.5 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}, \\ 0.7 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly μ is a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X . It is verified that μ restricted to a subset $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ which is a subalgebra of X is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , i.e., $\mu_{\{0,1,2,3\}} : \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . Thus $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X . Note that $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is not a fuzzy subalgebra of X , since $\mu(5 * 4) = \mu(0) = 0.5 \not\geq \min\{\mu(5), \mu(4)\} = 0.7$.

Sun Shin Ahn¹ and Young Joo Seo²

Example 3.3. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra ([1]) with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	4	4
1	1	0	0	1	4	4
2	2	2	0	2	4	4
3	3	3	3	0	4	4
4	4	4	4	0	0	
5	5	4	4	5	1	0

Define a map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) := \begin{cases} 0.5 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2\} \\ 0.7 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly μ is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . It is verified that μ restricted to a subset $\{0, 1, 2\}$ which is an ideal of X is a fuzzy ideal of X , i.e., $\mu_{\{0,1,2\}} : \{0, 1, 2\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of X . Thus $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . Note that $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is not a fuzzy ideal of X , since $\mu(2) = 0.5 \not\geq \min\{\mu(2*4) = \mu(4), \mu(4)\} = \mu(4) = 0.7$.

Lemma 3.4. Every Smarandache fuzzy ideal μ_P of a Smarandache BCI-algebra X is order reversing.

Proof. Let P be a BCK-algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|P| \geq 2$. If $x, y \in P$ with $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$. Hence we have $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y)$. \square

Theorem 3.5. Any Smarandache fuzzy ideal μ_P of a Smarandache BCI-algebra X must be a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof. Let P be a BCK-algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|X| \geq 2$. Since $x * y \leq x$ for any $x, y \in P$, it follows from Lemma 3.4 that $\mu(x) \leq \mu(x * y)$, so by (SF_2) we obtain $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$. This shows that μ is a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X , proving the theorem. \square

Proposition 3.6. Let μ_P be a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of a Smarandache BCI-algebra X . If the inequality $x * y \leq z$ holds in P , then $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(z)\}$ for all $x, y, z \in P$.

Proof. Let P be a BCK-algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|P| \geq 2$. If $x * y \leq z$ in P , then $(x * y) * z = 0$. Hence we have $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(z)\} = \mu(z)$. It follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$. \square

Theorem 3.7. Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra μ_P of X is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X if and only if for all $x, y \in P$, the inequality $x * y \leq z$ implies $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$.

Proof. Suppose that μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X satisfying the condition $x * y \leq z$ implies $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$. Since $x * (x * y) \leq y$ for all $x, y \in P$, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . The converse follows from Proposition 3.6. \square

Definition 3.8. Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X if it satisfies (SF_1) and

$$(SF_3) \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * x)) * z, \mu(z)\} \text{ for all } x, y, z \in P,$$

Smarandache fuzzy BCI-algebras

where $P \subsetneq X$ and P is a BCK-algebra with $|P| \geq 2$. This Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal is denoted by μ_P , i.e., $\mu_P : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X .

Example 3.9. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra ([2]) with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	1	0	0	0	0	5
2	2	1	0	1	0	5
3	3	4	4	4	0	5
4	4	4	4	4	0	5
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Define a map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) := \begin{cases} 0.4 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \\ 0.8 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly μ is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X , but μ is not a fuzzy clean ideal of X , since $\mu(3) = 0.4 \not\geq \min\{\mu((3 * (0 * 3)) * 5), \mu(5)\} = \min\{\mu(5), \mu(5)\} = \mu(5) = 0.8$.

Theorem 3.10. Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. Any Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal μ_P of X must be a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Let X be a BCK-algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|P| \geq 2$. Let $\mu_P : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X . If we let $y := x$ in (SF_3) , then $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (x * x)) * z), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu((x * 0) * z), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(x * z), \mu(z)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in P$. This shows that μ satisfies (SF_2) . Combining (SF_1) , μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X , proving the theorem. □

Corollary 3.11. Every Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal μ_P of a Smarandache BCI-algebra X must be a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof. It follows from Theorem 3.5 and Theorem 3.10. □

The converse of Theorem 3.10 may not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.12. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	1	0	1	0	0	5
2	2	2	0	0	0	5
3	3	3	3	0	0	5
4	4	3	4	1	0	5
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Let μ_P be a fuzzy set in $P = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ defined by $\mu(0) = \mu(2) = 0.8$ and $\mu(1) = \mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.3$. It is easy to check that μ_P is a fuzzy ideal of X . Hence $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . But it is not a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X since $\mu(1) = 0.3 \not\geq \min\{\mu((1 * (3 * 1)) * 2), \mu(2)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(2)\} = 0.8$.

Theorem 3.13. Let X be a Smarandache implicative BCI-algebra. Every Smarandache fuzzy ideal μ_P of X is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X .

Sun Shin Ahn¹ and Young Joo Seo²

Proof. Let P be a BCK -algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|P| \geq 2$. Since X is a Smarandache implicative BCI -algebra, we have $x = x * (y * x)$ for all $x, y \in P$. Let μ_P be a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . It follows from (SF_2) that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * z), \mu(z)\} \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in P$. Hence μ_P is a Smarandache clean ideal of X . The proof is complete. \square

In what follows, we give characterizations of fuzzy implicative ideals.

Theorem 3.14. *Let X be a Smarandache BCI -algebra. Suppose that μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . Then the following equivalent:*

- (i) μ_P is Smarandache fuzzy clean,
- (ii) $\mu(x) \geq \mu(x * (y * x))$ for all $x, y \in P$,
- (iii) $\mu(x) = \mu(x * (y * x))$ for all $x, y \in P$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Let μ_P be a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X . It follows from (SF_3) that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * 0), \mu(0)\} = \min\{\mu(x * (y * x)), \mu(0)\} = \mu(x * (y * x))$, $\forall x, y \in P$. Hence the condition (ii) holds.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Since X is a Smarnadache BCI -algebra, we have $x * (y * x) \leq x$ for all $x, y \in P$. It follows from Lemma 3.4 that $\mu(x) \leq \mu(x * (y * x))$. By (ii), $\mu(x) \geq \mu(x * (y * x))$. Thus the condition (iii) holds.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i): Suppose that the condition (iii) holds. Since μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal, by (SF_2) , we have $\mu(x * (y * x)) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\}$. Combining (iii), we obtain $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\}$. Hence μ satisfies the condition (SF_3) . Obviously, μ satisfies (SF_1) . Therefore μ is a fuzzy clean ideal of X . Hence the condition (i) holds. The proof is complete. \square

For any fuzzy sets μ and ν in X , we write $\mu \leq \nu$ if and only if $\mu(x) \leq \nu(x)$ for any $x \in X$.

Definition 3.15. Let X be a Smarandache BCI -algebra and let $\mu_P : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a Smarandache fuzzy BCI -algebra of X . For $t \leq \mu(0)$, the set $\mu_t := \{x \in P | \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a *level subset* of μ_P .

Theorem 3.16. *A fuzzy set μ in P is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X if and only if, for all $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is either empty or a Smarandache clean ideal of X .*

Proof. Suppose that μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ for any $t \in [0, 1]$. It is clear that $0 \in \mu_t$ since $\mu(0) \geq t$. Let $\mu((x * (y * x)) * z) \geq t$ and $\mu(z) \geq t$. It follows from (SF_3) that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\} \geq t$, namely, $x \in \mu_t$. This shows that μ_t is a Smarandache clean ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that for each $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is either empty or a Smaranadche clean ideal of X . For any $x \in P$, let $\mu(x) = t$. Then $x \in \mu_t$. Since $\mu_t (\neq \emptyset)$ is a Smarandache clean ideal of X , therefore $0 \in \mu_t$ and hence $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) = t$. Thus $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in P$. Now we show that μ satisfies (SF_3) . If not, then there exist $x', y', z' \in P$ such that $\mu(x') < \min\{\mu((x' * (y' * z')) * z'), \mu(z')\}$. Taking $t_0 := \frac{1}{2}\{\mu(x') + \min\{\mu((x' * (y' * z')) * z'), \mu(z')\}\}$, we have $\mu(x') < t_0 < \min\{\mu((x' * (y' * z')) * z'), \mu(z')\}$. Hence $x' \notin \mu_{t_0}$, $(x' * (y' * z')) * z \in \mu_{t_0}$, and $z' \in \mu_{t_0}$, i.e., μ_{t_0} is not a Smarandache clean of X , which is a contradiction. Therefore, μ_P is a Smarnadche fuzzy clean ideal, completing the proof. \square

Theorem 3.17. ([2]) (Extension Property) *Let X be a Smarandache BCI -algebra. Let I and J be Q -Smarandache ideals of X and $I \subseteq J \subseteq Q$. If I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X , then so is J .*

Next we give the extension theorem of Smarandache fuzzy clean ideals.

Smarandache fuzzy BCI-algebras

Theorem 3.18. *Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. Let μ and ν be Smarandache fuzzy ideals of X such that $\mu \leq \nu$ and $\mu(0) = \nu(0)$. If μ is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X , then so is ν .*

Proof. It suffices to show that for any $t \in [0, 1]$, ν_t is either empty or a Smarandache clean ideal of X . If the level subset ν_t is non-empty, then $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ and $\mu_t \subseteq \nu_t$. In fact, if $x \in \mu_t$, then $t \leq \mu(x)$; hence $t \leq \nu(x)$, i.e, $x \in \nu_t$. So $\mu_t \subseteq \nu_t$. By the hypothesis, since μ is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X , μ_t is a Smarandache clean of X by Theorem 3.16. It follows from Theorem 3.17 that ν_t is a Smarandache clean ideal of X . Hence ν is a Smarandache fuzzy clean of X . The proof is complete. □

Definition 3.19. Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a *Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal* of X if it satisfies (SF_1) and

$$(SF_4) \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y * z)\} \text{ for all } x, y, z \in P,$$

where P is a BCK-algebra with $P \subsetneq X$ and $|P| \geq 2$. This Smarandache fuzzy ideal is denoted by μ_P , i.e., $\mu_P : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of X .

Example 3.20. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra ([2]) with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	1	0	1	0	1	5
2	2	2	0	2	0	5
3	3	1	3	0	3	5
4	4	4	4	4	0	5
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Define a map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) := \begin{cases} 0.5 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 3\}, \\ 0.9 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly μ is a Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of X . But it is not a fuzzy fresh ideal of X , since $\mu(2 * 4) = \mu(0) = 0.5 \not\geq \min\{\mu((2 * 5) * 4), \mu(5 * 4)\} = \mu(5) = 0.9$.

Theorem 3.21. *Any Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of a Smarandache BCI-algebra X must be a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X .*

Proof. Taking $z := 0$ in (SF_4) and $x * 0 = x$, we have $\mu(x * 0) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * 0), \mu(y * 0)\}$. Hence $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. Thus (SF_2) holds. □

The converse of Theorem 3.21 may not be true as show in the following example.

Example 3.22. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a Smarandache BCI-algebra ([2]) with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	1	0	0	0	1	5
2	2	1	0	1	2	5
3	3	1	1	0	3	5
4	4	4	4	4	0	5
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Sun Shin Ahn¹ and Young Joo Seo²

Define a map $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) := \begin{cases} 0.5 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 4\}, \\ 0.4 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly $\mu(x)$ is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X . But $\mu(x)$ is not a Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of X , since $\mu(2 * 3) = \mu(1) = 0.4 \not\geq \min\{\mu((2 * 1) * 3), \mu(1 * 3)\} = \min\{\mu(1 * 3), \mu(0)\} = \mu(0) = 0.5$.

Proposition 3.23. *Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A Smarandache fuzzy ideal μ_P of X is a Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the condition $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu((x * y) * y)$ for all $x, y \in P$.*

Proof. Assume that μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy fresh ideal of X . Putting $z := y$ in (SF_4) , we have $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * y), \mu(y * y)\} = \min\{\mu((x * y) * y), \mu(0)\} = \mu((x * y) * y), \forall x, y \in P$.

Conversely, let μ_P be Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X such that $\mu(x * y) \geq \mu((x * y) * y)$. Since, for all $x, y, z \in P$, $((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z$, we have $\mu((x * y) * z) \leq \mu(((x * z) * z) * (y * z))$. Hence $\mu(x * z) \geq \mu((x * z) * z) \geq \min\{\mu(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), \mu(y * z)\} \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y * z)\}$. This completes the proof. \square

Since $(x * y) * y \leq x * y$, it follows from Lemma 3.4 that $\mu(x * y) \leq \mu((x * y) * y)$. Thus we have the following theorem.

Theorem 3.24. *Let X be a Smarandache BCI-algebra. A Smarandache fuzzy ideal μ_P of X is a Smarandache fuzzy fresh if and only if it satisfies the identity*

$$\mu(x * y) = \mu((x * y) * y), \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

We give an equivalent condition for which a Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra of a Smarandache BCI-algebra to be a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X .

Theorem 3.25. *A Smarandache fuzzy subalgebra μ_P of X is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X if and only if it satisfies*

$$(x * (y * x)) * z \leq u \text{ implies } \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z), \mu(u)\} \text{ for all } x, y, z, u \in P. \quad (*)$$

Proof. Assume that μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X . Let $x, y, z, u \in P$ be such that $(x * (y * x)) * z \leq u$. Since μ is a Smarandache fuzzy ideal of X , we have $\mu(x * (y * x)) \geq \min\{\mu(z), \mu(u)\}$ by Theorem 3.7. By Theorem 3.14-(iii), we obtain $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z), \mu(u)\}$.

Conversely, suppose that μ_P satisfies $(*)$. Obviously, μ_P satisfies (SF_1) , since $(x * (y * x)) * ((x * (y * x)) * z) \leq z$, by $(*)$, we obtain $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\}$, which shows that μ_P satisfies (SF_3) . Hence μ_P is a Smarandache fuzzy clean ideal of X . The proof is complete. \square

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. B. Jun, *Smarandache BCI-algebras*, Sci. Math. Japo. **62(1)** (2005), 137–142; e2005, 271–276.
- [2] Y. B. Jun, *Smarandache fresh and clean ideals of Smarandache BCI-algebras*, Kyungpook Math. J. **46** (2006), 409–416.
- [3] J. Meng and Y. B. Jun, *BCK-algebras*, Kyung Moon Sa, Seoul, 1994.

Smarandache fuzzy *BCI*-algebras

- [4] R. Padilla, *Smarandache algebraic structures*, Bull. Pure Sci. Delhi, **17E** (1998), no.1, 119–121;<http://www.gallup.unm.edu/smarandache/alg-s-tx.txt>.